

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Kadirova Marg'uba Buriyevna

TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR AS A LANGUAGE MATERIAL

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/MAY

